

Hyperlipidaemia in Equine, Canine and Feline

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Introduction

Hyperlipidemia is defined by the presence of elevated lipid concentrations in blood and are typically associated with periods of negative energy balance and physiologic stress. This increase in circulating lipids represent a normal physiologic response that serves to mobilize the energy reserves present in the fat depots of the body, but under certain circumstances, this response can become exaggerated and inappropriate. In increased concentration, circulating lipids typically occur in the triglyceride form and moderate increases in serum triglyceride concentration can lead to minor complications, with the most common being anorexia and depression. Increasing triglyceride concentration can interfere with numerous normal physiological functions, particularly in regard to reducing insulin sensitivity, this interference result in exacerbation of hyperlipidemias by impairing ability of the body to limit fat mobilization, leading to worsening of lipid accumulation and severe complication, including renal and hepatic lipidosis even death. Insulin resistant individuals are at risk for hyperlipidemias, with the most commonly affected animals being ponies, miniature horses and donkeys.

Hyperlipidaemia in Equine:

Disorders of Equine Fat Metabolism:

Dyslipidaemias are disorders of lipid metabolism associated with abnormal amounts of circulating lipids. In horses, dyslipidaemias present as hyperlipidaemias, characterized by accumulation of circulating lipids in the form of triglycerides. Hyperlipidaemias are most common in miniature horses, ponies, and donkeys but are uncommon in horses. (Hughes *et al.*, 2004) Hypertriglyceridemia is present

when serum triglyceride concentrations exceed the normal range (100 mg/dL) but is not associated with the evidence of clinical disease. Hyperlipidaemia is characterized by serum triglyceride concentrations from 100 to 500 mg/dL without gross lipaemia. Lipaemia describes the presence of gross turbidity in a blood sample because of the presence of high concentrations of Triglycerides but does not refer to a clinical syndrome. Severe hypertriglyceridemia is defined as serum triglyceride concentrations exceeding 500 mg/dL, but in the absence of gross lipemia, which differentiates this condition from hyperlipemia. (Dunkel B *et al.*, 2003; McGowan *et al.*, 2004). Hyperlipaemia is defined as a serum triglyceride concentration more than 500 mg/dL with visible lipemia and fatty infiltration of the liver or multiple organ systems (Naylor, 1982).

Disturbances Of Energy Metabolism

Equine Hyperlipidemias	Serum Triglyceride Concentration (mg/dL)	Gross Lipemia	Fatty Infiltration of Organs	Clinical Disease	Breeds Affected
Hypertriglyceridemia	>100	No	No	No	All
Hyperlipidemia	<500	No	No	No	All
Severe Hypertriglyceridemia	>500	No	Rare	Rare	Large-breed horses
Hyperlipemia	>500	Yes	Yes	Yes	Predisposed: ponies, miniature horses, donkeys Rare: large-breed horses

Several factors can contribute to abnormalities of energy metabolism in equids, with the most common apparent cause being insulin resistance. Fasting has been shown to induce a state of insulin resistance in normal ponies, whereas diets high in sugars and starches decrease insulin sensitivity in Thoroughbred weanlings and geldings. (Treiber *et al.*, 2005) Physical inactivity and increasing age also contribute to the development of insulin resistance. (McGowan *et al.*, 2004) Moreover, obese ponies and horses as well as ponies that have had laminitis are insulin resistant as compared with normal ponies or horses. The association of obesity, insulin resistance, hyperinsulinemia, and hypertriglyceridemia with laminitis, particularly in ponies, has led to the characterization of the equine metabolic syndrome. (Geor and frank, 2009) In animals, with any or all of the aforementioned risk factors, the development of a

negative energy balance can induce an inappropriate and excessive mobilization of peripheral fat stores. The liberated FFAs are converted into triglycerides within the liver, and the exported VLDLs accumulate within the circulation to excessive levels. (Watson *et al.*, 1992) The increased circulating concentrations of FFAs and triglycerides can further complicate the normal homeostatic mechanisms that regulate energy metabolism, primarily by interfering with the actions of insulin. By preventing insulin from suppressing the activity of HSL, the rate of tissue lipolysis increases, worsening the hypertriglyceridemia. It has been shown that increased circulating FFA concentrations lead to the accumulation of lipid metabolites in muscle and hepatic tissue. (Shulman, 2000) This accumulation disrupts the normal pathways that are responsible for insulin-induced glucose uptake in skeletal muscles and interferes with gluconeogenesis in the liver.

Diagnosis

The clinical signs of hyperlipidaemias are nonspecific but most commonly include depression, anorexia, and decreased water intake. (Dunkel and McKenzie, 2003) More severe signs may include colic, fever, diarrhoea, cachexia, and ventral oedema. (Naylor, 1982) Serum triglyceride concentration should be measured as part of a routine serum biochemical evaluation in ponies, miniature horses, or donkeys because of their predisposition to hyperlipidaemias and in hospitalized horses of all breeds because stress, illness, and hypophagia are common in the hospitalized population. Hematologic changes are nonspecific and typically related to underlying disease processes but may include haemoconcentration, neutrophilia, neutropenia, left shift, and hyperfibrinogenaemia. Metabolic acidosis is common in affected animals. Azotaemia is also frequent and may reflect either prerenal azotaemia and/or renal dysfunction secondary to renal lipidosis. Hepatic involvement may be demonstrated by increases in the serum bilirubin concentration as well as the hepatocellular and biliary enzyme levels. (Dunkel and McKenzie, 2003)

Management of Hyperlipidaemia in Equine

- Correction of Negative Energy Balance (Durham, 2006)
- Nutritional Support (Magdesian, 2010)
- Insulin therapy (Durham, 2006)

Gross lipemia in a serum sample (left) as compared with a normal sample (right).

Hyperlipidaemia in Canine:

Simplified illustrating the basics of lipoprotein metabolism in dogs.

Table 1. Causes of hyperlipidaemia in dogs		
	Type of lipid abnormality	Comments
Postprandial hyperlipidaemia*	HTG (rarely HCH)	Increases are typically mild and last <15 hours Most common cause of hyperlipidaemia
High-fat diets	HTG and/or HCH	Fat content must be very high (typically >50%) to cause hyperlipidaemia
Secondary hyperlipidaemia		
Endocrine disease		
Diabetes mellitus*	HTG (mainly) and/or HCH	HTG and HCH can range from mild to marked; present in >50% of cases
Hypothyroidism*	HTG and/or HCH	HTG and HCH can range from mild to marked; present in >75% of cases
Hyperadrenocorticism*	HTG and/or HCH	HTG and HCH can range from mild to marked
Pancreatitis*	HTG and/or HCH	Both HTG and HCH are typically mild if other causes of hyperlipidemia are not present; present in ~30% of cases
Obesity*	HTG and/or HCH	HTG and HCH can range from mild to marked; present in >25% of cases
Protein-losing nephropathy*	HCH	HCH is part of the nephrotic syndrome; HCH is usually mild
Cholestasis*	HTG and/or HCH	Increases are usually mild
Hepatic insufficiency*	HTG and/or HCH	Increases are usually mild
Lymphoma	HTG with or without HCH	Hyperlipidaemia might persist despite treatment
<i>Leishmania infantum</i> infection	HTG and HCH	Increases are typically mild if present
Parvoviral enteritis	HTG	HTG is typically mild if present
Hypnatraemia?	HTG and HCH	Based on a case report and evidence from human medicine
Drugs*		
Glucocorticoids	HTG and/or HCH	Increases can range from mild to marked
Phenobarbital	HTG	HTG can range from mild to marked; present in >30% of cases
Estrogen/progesterone?	HTG and/or HCH	Anecdotal
Primary hyperlipidaemia		
Miniature Schnauzer*	HTG with or without HCH	It is usually breed specific but can appear in any dog HTG can range from mild to marked; HCH may be mild to moderate; present in >30% of all dogs in the USA; prevalence increases with age
Beagle*	HTG and/or HCH	Increases are usually mild to moderate
Shetland sheepdog*	HCH with or without HTG	HCH might be marked; HTG is typically mild; present in >40% of dogs in Japan
Dobermann	HCH	HCH is usually mild
Rottweiler	HCH	HCH is usually mild
Briard	HCH	HCH in Briards has only been reported in the UK
Rough-coated Collie	HCH	Reported in a single family in the UK
Pyrenees Mountain dogs	HCH	HCH is usually mild

HTG hypertriglyceridemia, HCH hypercholesterolaemia
*Indicates common causes

Treatment

Treatment of hyperlipidaemia in canine includes;

- Dietary management
- Medical management
 - Omega-3 fatty acids (fish oil)
 - Fibrates (fabric acid derivatives)
 - Niacin (nicotinic acid)
 - Statins (Lipid-lowering drugs) (Xenoulis and Steiner, 2010)

Hyperlipidaemia in Feline

A raised blood concentrations of lipid in the fasted patient (> 12 hours) exceeding the upper range of normal.

Causes: Primary Idiopathic and Secondary to another disease process.

Etiology

Primary hyperlipidaemia:

- Idiopathic hyperchylomicronaemia.

Genetic predisposition in Himalayan cats - autosomal recessive gene:

- **Post-prandial hypertriglyceridaemia.**

Secondary hyperlipidaemia:

- Same as primary causative disease process.

Specific:

- Obesity
- Higher intake of fat
- Hyperchylomicronaemia- Genetic predisposition in Himalayan breed.

Pathophysiology

An increase in blood lipid concentrations in the fasted patient exceeding upper range of normal: primary idiopathic or secondary to another disease process.

Primary hyperlipidaemia:

Idiopathic hyperchylomicronaemia:

Defective lipoprotein lipase (LPL) activity → hypertriglyceridemia + hyperchylomicronemia.

Post-prandial hyperlipidaemia:

30-60 minutes after ingestion of meal containing fat → gastrointestinal absorption of chylomicrons → increase in serum triglycerides for 3-10 hours.

Secondary hyperlipidaemia:

- **Pancreatitis**

Pancreatic inflammation may compromise pancreatic insulin production → reduced LPL activity → hyperlipidaemia (hypertriglyceridemia, +/- moderate hypercholesterolemia).

- **Diabetes mellitus:**

Reduced LPL activity + increased very low-density lipoprotein (VLDL) production → hyperlipidaemia (hypertriglyceridemia, moderate hypercholesterolemia).

- **Hyperadrenocorticism:**

Rare in cats and this is often associated with diabetes mellitus which may account for hyperlipidaemia. Reduced LPL activity + increased hepatic synthesis of VLDL → hypercholesterolaemia + hypertriglyceridaemia.

- **Nephrotic syndrome Nephrotic syndrome:**

Low albumin and low oncotic pressure → increased hepatic cholesterol synthesis.

- **Liver disease Liver: chronic disease/cholestasis:**
Reduced cholesterol excretion in bile → hypercholesterolemia.
- **Obesity:**
Increased hepatic VLDL synthesis → hyperlipidaemia.
- **Ocular hyperlipidaemia:** High serum lipoproteins → anterior uveitis → normal blood aqueous barrier breakdown → lipids enter aqueous humor → cloudy eye + *Lipemia retinalis* may → blindness. This can be seen with both primary and secondary hyperlipidaemias.

Time course:

Usually chronic (In months).

Signs: Mostly asymptomatic; vomiting, diarrhea, seizures, abdominal pain, distress, ocular involvement; and in secondary hyperlipidaemia - signs of primary causative disease process.

Diagnosis: Serum biochemistry with serum triglyceride, refrigeration test, lipid and cholesterol concentrations; lipoprotein electrophoresis.

Treatment: Reduce dietary fat and / or treatment of primary disease process.

Prognosis: Dependent upon response to treatment of primary disease process.

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